

Datum 2022-11-27
Dnr 2021-3125
Handläggare Elyse Canosa
Bilder

Light microscopy instrument report

Samples

Type reference material art object/artifact

Form paint flakes from models (unaged and aged) of painting (Konstnärnsförbundets styrelse, by Richard Bergh)

Colour various

Age new made

Material oil paint on Canvas

Concentrations N/A

Point of analysis See specific points of analysis for the different samples in 'Provtagningsprotokoll'.

Sample/Object	#	specifics
Un-aged canvas	UA3C1	w Zn white
	UA3C2	w/o Zn white
	UA1CB	w/o Zn white
Aged canvas	A3C1	w Zn white
	A3C2	w/o Zn white
	A1CB	w/o Zn white

Purpose

To investigate if and how the ageing conditions have induced soap formation within the paint layers, especially the models based on Zn-white.

Method

Sample preparation

Samples were embedded in Technovit2000, exposed to blue light between 10-30 min and 2 hours before wet-polishing.

Light microscopy instrument parameters

Riksantikvarieämbetet
Artillerigatan 33
Box 1114
621 22 Visby
Tel 08-5191 8000
E-post registrator@raa.se
Hemsida www.raa.se
Org.nr 202100-1090

Microscope: Nikon Eclipse LV100ND

Camera fitted on microscope: Nikon Digital Sight 10

- Reflected light
- Transmitted light
- Darkfield
- Brightfield
- Cool LED pE-300 white (fluorescence)
- Semrock DAPI 5060C (Blue bandpass filter, excitation 377/50 nm, emission 447/60 nm)
- Semrock GFP-30LP-B (Green longpass filter, excitation 472/30 nm, emission 496 LP)
- Semrock GFP-3035D (Green bandpass, excitation 472/30 nm, emission 520/35 nm)
- Chroma AT UV/D LP (Blue longpass filter, excitation 375/26 nm, emission 435 LP)
- Polariser adapter for cross-polarised light
- Retardation plate
- Compensator
- Bertrand lens
- Chelsea filter
- Wave plate

Results

UA3C1

UA3C1 x5, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C1 x10, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C1 x20, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

UA3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV

UA3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter

UA3C2

UA3C2 x5, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C2 x10, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C2 x20, Darkfield, VIS

UA3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

UA3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV

UA3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter

UA1CB

UA1CB x5, Darkfield, VIS

UA1CB x10, Darkfield, VIS

UA1CB x20, Darkfield, VIS

UA1CB x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

UA1CB x20, Darkfield, UV

UA1CB x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter

A3C1

A3C1 x5, Darkfield, VIS

A3C1 x10, Darkfield, VIS

A3C1 x20, Darkfield, VIS

A3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

A3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV

A3C1 x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter

A3C2

A3C2 x5, Darkfield, VIS

A3C2 x10, Darkfield, VIS

A3C2 x20, Darkfield, VIS

A3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

A3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV

A3C2 x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter

A1CB

A1CB x5, Darkfield, VIS

A1CB x10, Darkfield, VIS

A1CB x20, Darkfield, VIS

A1CB x20, Darkfield, UV, Blue long pass filter

A1CB x20, Darkfield, UV

A1CB x20, Darkfield, UV, Green long pass filter